

METHODOLOGY OF USING PIRLS TASKS IN FORMING SPEAKING COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

Orazova Sultonposhsha Kahramon kizi

Urganch State Pedagogical Institute

Methodology of the theory of education (primary education)

1st year master's student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10057047>

Annotation: This article provides general information about the methodology of using PIRLS tasks in the formation of speech competence in primary school students.

Key words: international evaluation programs, PISA, PIRLS, foreign experiences, national center for evaluation of educational quality, professional competence, reading literacy, level of understanding, educational system.

PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) is an international assessment system that assesses the quality of reading and comprehension levels of primary school students in different countries. This type of test is designed to be held once every 5 years, and the participation of Uzbekistani students in the research planned for 2021 places a great responsibility on primary education teachers.

The implementation of this important task requires a new approach to education, activity from the teacher. At this point, the question of how to prepare a student for PIRLS, which determines the level of international assessment, raises many questions.

In the systematic preparation for PIRLS, the role of extracurricular reading, reinforcement, revision lessons and clubs is very important. It is very important to expand the student's worldview, develop independent thinking, imaginative thinking.

The goals of PIRLS are not limited to literacy. Research collects information related to students' reading skills (social background, study habits, teaching strategies, etc.) and helps to understand individual and social conditions in a school or classroom.

One of the most important requirements for international PIRLS studies is the use of assignments that allow for comparative analysis. Therefore, in the process of forming tasks, the block of control materials used in previous years was used. Also, the main focus is on standardization of the research process.

For this reason, PIRLS research is carried out on the basis of a strictly defined single instruction. Based on the conceptual ideas of the research, 4 types of reading skills are evaluated when evaluating the level of reading artistic and popular scientific texts:

- finding information given in a clear form;
- forming conclusions based on the read text;
- summarizing and interpreting information;
- assessing and analyzing the structure of the text, the content of language features.

The following evaluation system is used to evaluate the works performed within PIRLS based on quantity and quality indicators:

- tasks related to choosing the answer with 1 point;
- tasks and decisions related to events and sequence of events with 1 point;

Open-ended, constructive assignments with written answers are rated from 1 to 3 points depending on the level of difficulty.

35 countries took part in the study organized in 2001, 215 thousand students from 40 countries took part in the 2006 study, and 325 thousand students from 45 countries took part in 2011. In these studies, 4th grade students from Hong Kong, Finland and Singapore recorded the highest results[1].

PIRLS research examines the following two types of reading most commonly used by students in class:

Reading for the purpose of acquiring the qualification of literary reading.

Reading to understand and apply the content.

Students are given two tasks:

1. Learning the experience of literary reading;
2. Development and use of information.

The basis of reading literacy is the formation of reading skills necessary to fully work with texts. This is the ability of the reader to find and distribute the necessary information, draw conclusions about a certain part of the text, interpret the actions of the main characters, confirm the text samples and text structure with preliminary analysis.

One of the main tasks of PIRLS is to study the dynamics of the quality of education. A necessary condition for reading is to reuse a part of the texts and tasks assigned to them in each part.

The concept of speech and its development. Speech is a type of human activity, the use of thinking based on language tools (words, phrases, sentences). Speech performs the function of communication and message, emotional expression and influence of mutual opinion. A well-developed speech serves as one of the important tools of a person's active activity in society. And for the student, speech is a tool for successful learning at school. What is speech development? If the student and his/her language activities are taken into account, speech development means active and practical acquisition of the language in all aspects (pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure, connected speech). In the case of a teacher, speech development means the use of methods and types of work that help students acquire language pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic construction, and connected speech as an important asset. For speech activity, as well as for the development of students' speech, it is necessary to observe several conditions:

1. There must be a requirement for human speech to surface. The methodical requirement for the development of students' speech is to create a situation where the student expresses his opinion, something orally or in writing, creates a desire and necessity.

- 2.. Any speech should have content and material. The more complete, rich, and valuable this material is, the more meaningful its description will be.

3. An idea is understandable only if it is expressed using words, phrases, sentences, and speech phrases that the listener understands. Therefore, the third condition for successful development of speech is arming speech with language tools. A number of clearly defined requirements are followed in the development of students' speech.

1. Let students' speech be meaningful.

International experts evaluate reading literacy according to the quality of reading literary and informational texts and the scale of assessment of individual groups of reading ability.[2]

In the process of reading the text, the needs of the students are also important. As the student's literacy increases, his goals begin to change. If you just read the text before, now this need becomes more complicated, that is, processes such as understanding the behavior of the character, determining his goals and even predicting his next actions occur. Taking into account the age of the student, the use of illustrative texts can be used to enrich the student's imagination, to quickly understand the meaning of the text through pictures, and to increase his interest.

Reading is directly related to oral speech and helps to form expressive reading skills, to engage in communication among students through mutual discussion and analysis of information in the text. In elementary school, logical thinking is not as developed as in adults, so they use more visual imagination. Having a visual understanding of objects, animals or objects found in the text, and then thinking about them regularly, students begin to develop logical thinking.

Four qualities should not be overlooked in the development of reading skills: correct and error-free reading, fluent reading, reading comprehension, and expressive reading.[3]

Correct reading means reading without distorting the meaning of words and following literary norms; in fluent reading - the speed of reading the text is understood, usually how many words are read in one minute; to understand is to convey the main content of the text to the listener and express his attitude; Expressive reading is reading with pauses and intonations, observing punctuation marks. Visual aids and pictures are very helpful in students' ability to show the emotional states of the heroes of the work, to express a certain feeling, for example, sadness, happiness. The situation of the heroes of the fairy tales, simulating their actions, solving riddles quickly or being affected by the events that happened when they read the stories also depend on the emotional state of the readers.

In preparing students for PIRLS, it is important to have an integrated approach and connections with the studied objects, to activate mental activity in learning, to develop visual perceptions, to find conclusions, to find additional information not only on educational materials, but also in everyday life. According to PIRLS research, reading literacy is the ability to understand and use the forms of written language required by society and valued by people, as well as the ability to create meaning from texts in various forms. This view of reading literacy as a constructive and interactive process reflects many theories of reading.[4]

Interactive process is the creation of information through communication between the student and the text during the student's work with the text.

Constructive process, the reader creates meaning on the basis of given non-standard texts. The word "constructive" is derived from the English word "construct" and means to create. The reader is an active participant in this process, creating meaning, reflecting on the text, and consciously choosing effective reading strategies. Each type of text follows typical patterns and rules to help the reader interpret the text. Any text can have different forms. These include traditional books, magazines, documents and newspapers, as well as written forms in digital form.

On the basis of the PIRLS standard, it is appropriate to organize the reading and understanding of students in the classroom and outside the classroom independently, and the teacher evaluates the interest, level of knowledge, and ability of the students.

The purpose of the PIRLS assessment program is to achieve the organization of the teaching process so that students gain artistic experience and receive and use information.

The main task of the teacher is to teach the child to get out of the situation and to think creatively, to correctly direct the abundance of information, to get the necessary information and to use it. The teacher should prepare students for real life, correct thinking, and conclusions.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No.
2. Decision No. 997 of December 8, 2018 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to organize international studies in the field of education quality assessment in the public education system.
3. A. Ismoilov, D. Norboyeva, K. Kucharova, Z. Kasimova, N. Aminova. Assessment of literacy of elementary school students in international studies. (study guide) - T.: Sharq, 2019. -94 p.
4. Assessment of students' reading literacy in international studies (Methodical guide for teachers of mother tongue and literature, methodologists and specialists) Chief editorial office of "Sharq" publishing-printing joint-stock company. Tashkent - 2019.